

A Study on the Saving Habits and Investment Behaviour of Employees after Retirement with Special Reference to Velur, Thrissur District, Kerala

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Abstract

Retirement is a process in each and every employee's life who gets into service. One has to switch off from his or her work after attaining of a certain age. One of the major problems faced by these employees after retirement is that, they are not able to control their expenses after retirement on a sudden. We know that the pension received, in case of government employees will be comparatively very less and to adjust their livelihood with this forms a major task. In the case of non-government employees, they don't receive anything at all on a regular monthly basis after retirement. They might get the gratuity plus any insurance policies taken by them at the time of retirement. So with this income they have to move their remaining life. So a proper planning of one's investment and involving in jobs to a certain period even after retirement would help one to live a better and peaceful life. The present study deals with the saving habits and investment behavior of retired Government employees with special reference to Velur, Thrissur District, Kerala and it is found that majority people wishes to invest their funds in safer zones than that of jumping into risky ventures. Especially these senior citizens are not interested to challenge their money in risky avenues as they fear off and look at their future with uncertainty in the form of ill health. But even then a good quantum of them is interested to invest in stock markets and related instruments as they would fetch higher profits if the stock market is favourable.

Keywords: Investment, Retirement, Savings, Risk, Return, Avenues

Introduction

Savings plays a vital role in the economic growth of any nation. With the savings invested in various options available to the people, the money acts as the driver for growth of the country. Indian financial system too offers a list of opportunities to the investors. Even though our financial system is not the outstanding one when compared with other nations, it provides good avenues for an individual who wishes to invest their money in the stock market. Investment benefits both economy and the society which in turn helps in the economic development and standard of living of the people. For the economy as a whole, aggregate investment sanctioned in the current period is a key factor in determining aggregate demand, the level of employment

and so on. And as such investment behaviour and saving habits is a necessity in each and everyone's life which contributes to greater economic growth and prosperity. The present study deals with the behaviour of the investor especially retired employees to identify their investment avenues with special reference to Velur, Thrissur District, Kerala.

Investor

An investor is one who makes an investment into one or more categories of assets-equity, debt securities, real estate, currency, commodity, derivatives such as put and call options, etc. with the objective of making a profit.

Investment

Investment refers to the concept of deferred consumption, which involves purchasing an asset, giving a loan or keeping funds in a bank account with the aim of generating future returns.

Investment Behaviour

Investment behaviours are defined as how the investor's judge, predict, analyse and review the procedures for decision making, which includes investment psychology, information gathering, defining and understanding, research and analysis.

Investment Strategy

The investment strategy is a plan, which is created to guide an investor to choose the most appropriate investment portfolio that will help them to achieve their financial goals within a particular period of time.

Brief History of Velur

Velur is a small village and Panchayat in Thalappilly Taluk, Thrissur district, Kerala with a population of 22,155. Other places close to Velur are Kechery, Wadakkanchery etc. It belongs to Central Kerala Division and is located 16 km towards North from district headquarters Thrissur, 7 km from Wadakkanchery and 297 km from State capital Thiruvananthapuram. This place is in the border of the Thrissur District and Palakkad District. Malayalam is the local language here. The total area comprises of 28.32 km² (10.93 sq. mi). The population of the village according to the sensex 2001 is 22,155 and the density of the same is 780/ km² (2000/sq. mi). Official Languages used are Malayalam and English. The sex ratio 0.89♂/♀ and has a literacy rate of 90.15%.

Objectives of the study

- To analyze the investment pattern of retired employees at Velur.
- To analyze the saving habits of retired employees
- To analyze the various avenues that is available for safer investment.
- To analyze the taste and preference of these employees towards risky investments.
- To analyze the present working status of employees after retirement.
- To study the various alternatives of investment which are available in the market.
- To find out how investors are motivated to invest in various financial instruments.

Statement of the Problem

In our society, especially within Kerala, we can find a good quantum of Retired Government employees. But now, as the cost of living has increased, they have keenly felt the need to work again for certain years for smooth flow of their life and to maintain a healthy body. The present study focuses on status of employees after retirement who performs certain investment activities in order to run their day to day lives.

Scope of the study

The present study is about the saving habits and investment behaviour of employees after retirement with special reference to Velur, Thrissur District, Kerala. The study measures the saving habits and investment strategies adopted by these employees and try to analyze the reasons for the same. The scope of the study is limited to this village due to constraints of time. There are similar other villages in the nearby locality where we can find numerous retired employees which are not taken into consideration by the researcher

Methodology

- The study is mainly based on primary data.
- Secondary data are also collected from articles and websites
- Direct personal interviews were made with the retired employees.

An Analysis on the Employee's Life Style after Retirement

It is very much necessary to scrutinize the way in which changes takes place in the expenditure of an individual who retires from a job or one comes to a close of a business. By retirement majority of heavy expenses which were dealt in the past will come to an end. Due to this the overall expenditure of an individual may reduce by 10 to 20%. Life after retirement can be divided into 3 parts or categories. The first stage of this starts from the age of retirement say 55, 56, 60 whatever may be to 65 years. The next stage commences from the age of 65 to till 75 and third stage and final stage is above 75 years.

In the first stage, travelling and other expenses would be high and so the total expenditure would also be high. In the second stage, majority of the people would try to spend their time in their respective households itself. Due to this reason, majority of unwanted expenses will be reduced and there would be a steep increase in medical expenditure. In the third and last stage, it may be sometimes necessary that these people may need the help of others for their day to day activities. Public expenses will be very less at his stage, but medical and nursing expenses will be very high.

One of the main incomes of a retiree will be the interest on the deposits which they have kept in the bank. From this they can find an income to meet the day to day expenditure. But due to increased cost of living, the prices of goods and services are increasing year by year. For example, in the year 2008, ½ litre milk costs Rs. 10 and now we have to pay Rs.20 for the same product with the same quantity. i.e., by 11 years the value of the products has doubled. That means per year approximately we can find an increase in price of 10%.

When we compare this particular aspect with fixed deposits in the year 2008, it was 9% and now in 2019, it has been decreased to 7%. That means for example, if in the year 2008, if we had got Rs.10,000 as interest for a fixed sum, for the same principal amount we would get only Rs. 7779 as interest for this deposit. At the same time, if Rs.10,000 was expended for any activity in the year 2008, we have to spend at least Rs. 20,000 at present to avail the same service, activity or product. So it is not at all easy for an individual to push their day to day lives only with this income.

Top 10 Investment Avenues available for the Senior Citizens are

Direct equity: Investing in stocks is highly risky as it's a volatile asset class and there is no guarantee of returns. Also, it is a tedious task for an individual to pick out the right stock that too in the correct timings. But one of the major highlighting advantages for the same is its ability to deliver higher returns if it gains momentum. At the same time, the risk of losing a considerable portion of capital is high.

Equity mutual funds: Equity mutual funds predominantly invest in equity stocks. As per current Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) Mutual Fund Regulations, an equity mutual fund scheme must invest at least 65 percent of its assets in equities and equity-related instruments. An equity fund can be actively managed or passively managed.

Debt mutual funds: Debt funds are ideal for investors who want steady returns. They are less volatile and, hence, less risky compared to equity funds. Debt mutual funds primarily invest in fixed-interest generating securities like corporate bonds, government securities, treasury bills, commercial paper and other money market instruments. Currently, the 1-, 3-, 5-year market return is around 6.5 percent, 8 percent, and 7.5 percent, respectively.

National Pension System (NPS): The National Pension System is a long term retirement - focused investment product managed by the Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority (PFRDA). The minimum annual (April-March) contribution for an NPS Tier-1 account to remain active has been reduced from Rs 6,000 to Rs 1,000. It is a mix of equity, fixed deposits, corporate bonds, liquid funds and government funds, among others. Based on one's risk appetite, one can decide how much money can be invested in equities through NPS. Currently, the 1-,3-,5-year market return for Fund option E is around 9.5 percent, 8.5 percent, and 11 percent, respectively.

Public Provident Fund (PPF): The Public Provident Fund is one product a lot of people turn to. Since the PPF has a long tenure of 15 years, the impact of compounding of tax-free interest is huge, especially in the later years. Further, since the interest earned and the principal invested is backed by sovereign guarantee, it makes it a safe investment.

Bank fixed deposit (FD): A bank fixed deposit is a safe choice for investing in India. Under the Deposit Insurance and Credit Guarantee Corporation (DICGC) rules, each depositor in a bank is insured up to a maximum of Rs. 1 lakh for both principal and interest amount.

Senior Citizens' Saving Scheme (SCSS): Probably the first choice of most retirees, the Senior Citizens' Saving Scheme is a must-have in their investment portfolios. As the name suggests, only senior citizens or early retirees can invest in this scheme. This can be availed from a post office or a bank by anyone above 60. SCSS has a five-year tenure, which can be further extended by three years once the scheme matures. Currently, the interest rate that can be earned on SCSS is 8.3 per cent per annum, payable quarterly and is fully taxable. The upper investment limit is Rs 15 lakh, and one may open more than one account.

RBI Taxable Bonds: The government has replaced the former 8 percent Savings (Taxable) Bonds 2003 with the 7.75 per cent Savings (Taxable) Bonds. These bonds come with tenure of 7 years. The bonds may be issued in demat form and credited to the Bond Ledger Account (BLA) of the investor and a Certificate of Holding is given to the investor as proof of investment.

Real Estate: Investments in real estate is really a good endeavor which yields return in the form of capital appreciation and rentals. When compared with other forms of assets, these are highly illiquid and the smooth transfer of the same from one person to another is very complicated due to coming of real estate regulator.

Gold: If one plans to possess gold as an investment, it has its own risk like safety and high cost. The making charges of gold ornaments typically range from 6 to 14% and 25% in certain cases. This may be unaffordable to certain people. So it would be better for them to buy coins. One can also purchase paper gold through ETFs. Such investment (buying and selling) happens on a stock exchange (NSE or BSE) with gold as the underlying asset. Investing in Sovereign Gold Bonds is another option to own paper-gold.

The present study comprises of 10 Government employees who have retired from varying fields at Velur and receives normal pension.

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Name	A	B	C	D	E	F
Occupation	Professor	Police	Teacher	Civil Engineer	Doctor	Police
Gender	Male	Male	Female	Male	Male	Male
Age	71	78	65	63	67	65
Present Occupation	Part Time Professor in a Self Financing College	Agri-cultural works	Office work in a private firm	Agricultural works	Practicing in a clinic	Working as security
Investment in Post Office	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Direct Equity	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Equity mutual funds	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Debt mutual funds	No	No	No	No	No	No
National Pension System (NPS)	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
Public Provident Fund (PPF)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bank fixed deposit (FD)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Senior Citizens' Saving Scheme (SCSS)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Real Estate	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
RBI Taxable Bonds	No	No	No	No	No	No
Gold	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Name	G	H	I	J	Total	%
Occupation of the employees	Electrical Engineer	Lawyer	Doctor	Teacher	Teacher-3 Lawyer-1 Police-2 Doctor-2 Engineer-2	Teacher-30% Lawyer-10% Police-20% Doctor-20% Engineer-20%
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Female	M - 8	80%
					F - 2	20%
Present Occupation	Electrical works in a private firm	Practicing as lawyer privately	Practicing in a clinic	Tuition classes	Working- 10 Not working-0	Working-100% Not working-0
Investment in Post Office	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes - 7	70%
					No - 3	30%

Direct Equity	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes - 3	30%
					No - 7	70%
Equity mutual funds	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes - 3	30%
					No - 7	70%
Equity mutual funds	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes - 3	30%
					No - 7	70%
Debt mutual funds	No	No	No	No	Yes - 7	70%
					No - 3	30%
National Pension System (NPS)	Yes	No	No	No	Yes - 2	20%
					No - 8	80%
Public Provident Fund (PPF)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes - 10	100%
					No - 0	0%
Bank fixed deposit (FD)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes - 10	100%
					No - 0	0%
Senior Citizens' Saving Scheme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes - 10	100%
					No - 0	0%
Real Estate	No	No	Yes	No	Yes - 6	60%
					No - 4	40%
RBI Taxable Bonds	No	No	No	No	Yes - 0	0%
					No - 10	100%
Gold	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes - 8	80%
					No - 3	20%

- It is scrutinized that out of 10 employees interviewed, 80% constitute male and balance 20% female.
- All employees are senior citizens above 60 years.
- Out of the interviewed employees Teacher constitutes 30%, Lawyer-10%, Police-20%, Doctor-20% and Engineer-20%
- All of them are employed in a way or the other even after retirement for the smooth flow of their lives.
- Around 70% of them have investments in Post Office savings scheme.
- 100% of the employees are a part of Public Provident Fund (PPF), Bank fixed deposit (FD) and Senior Citizens' Saving Scheme as the risk involved in these avenues is very less and the returns are attractive and safe as they are not interested to play with their funds in their old age due to fear of loss.
- Around 60% of them are interested in real estate business and have invested money in the same.
- None of them have investment in RBI taxable bonds.
- 30% of them have investment in equity shares and related instruments.
- Equity mutual funds have little demand @30% when compared debt mutual funds which has 70% subscription as the return is sure in case of debt funds.

- 20% of them are part of National Pension Scheme.
- 100% of them have investment in gold which is the normal form of investment from the past decade itself and considered to be a safe venture.

Findings

- Almost all retirees possess higher education like graduation and above.
- All the employees are government pensioners who are in a way or the other employed in a small basis.
- The investment habit was noted in a majority of the people who participated in the study.
- Most of them are choosing two or more sources of information to make investment decisions.
- These retirees discuss with their family and friends before making an investment decision. People make investments for increasing the rate of return on their savings and reducing the risk.
- Safety, liquidity and hedge against inflation are the major objectives when one enters into the pace of investment.
- Investors always desire to have a good rate of return from their investments in the past, present and in the forthcoming future.
- People are interested to invest in Post Office Savings Scheme as there is no anxiety about the future return.
- Many of them are not even aware of the stock market schemes.
- Most investors prefer to park their fund in avenues like Bank, Public Provident Fund, Senior Citizens Savings scheme, Mutual Funds and Gold.
- Majority of them are not interested to invest in capital market instruments due to the risk of loss of money.
- Increase in age decrease the risk tolerance level of risk which the intake.
- Women are attracted towards investing in gold than any other investment avenue.

Suggestions

Pensioners must not fully rely upon the fixed deposits itself after retirement. He or she must find other ways to acquire income to meet their day to day life. For this, it would be better if they go for a part time job, make investments in mutual funds and shares, debentures etc. They can go for part time jobs up to the age of 65. Even though, if we are having a good earning from other sources, it would be better off to continue with such jobs which would help to keep us young and energetic. We might get salary as only a very small amount. It may be one third or one fifth of our income which we received during service, but it would be good to save one's investment and this would help to cover the day to day expenses without touching our fixed deposits.

Another method to make savings is through adoption of pension plans which is an appropriate investment strategy. This would help to acquire income till our life ends. But usually the problem we find is that the income received from this scheme is comparatively less. One of the famous pension plans is L.I.C.'s "JeevanAkshay". Its features are as follows. For a premium of Rs. 1,00,000, a senior citizen who attains the age of 60 will receive Rs. 7110 per month as pension. Not only that, this premium amount will be received back by the relatives of this individual after he or she expires. This pension scheme is somewhat equal to the bank interest. If in the plan after the death of the pensioner, if it is not necessary to give the principal amount to the legal heirs, then we will get Rs. 9350 per month as pension and this would be stopped by the death of the pensioner. This type of LIC plan should be adopted only when one reaches the third stage. At this time, we find hard to travel from one place to another. So it would be better if we get an income in our hands without

any efforts during these periods. Not only that, as the life span of the individual is less during this time, the amount which we receive as premium would be higher and more attractive.

Once an individual moves to the pace of retirement he has to make a calculation of all his expenses, try to reduce the same, and must take that plan which provides maximum satisfaction and safety.

Another method to accumulate revenue after retirement is as follows

If one gets a lumpsum amount at the time of retirement, we can use the same for the purchase of commercial property and can rent the same in the form of office space or shops. Thereby the amount which we had invested for the purchase of this commercial property can be recouped within a short span of time. We would receive income on this rented property which would yield an amount of 6 to 7% of the principal amount which we had spent for the purchase of the same. Not only that, along with this, the rate of rent goes on stepping forward high @ 5 to 7%. So even if there arises inflation, it won't affect at all and within years the price of property will shoot up. When one reaches the third stage of retirement, he or she can sell the same at a good price if needed. From this amount if one wants to take a pension plan, he or she can take one and the balance if willing can distribute to their children. There are people who are interested to start business after retirement. It is necessary that a person who had worked for a salary basis for a longer period may not become successful in a business if he adopts it as it requires expertise and tricks to compete in the market. But if one is confident to take the same, one can enter into the same. There is nothing wrong in it.

Finally the major investment avenue i.e., the stock market investment can be made by the individuals only if one has perfect knowledge about the same. It is found that these retired employees have a very little knowledge in the field of share market. In selection of appropriate portfolios, one must seek information from experts in this field as the risk associated with it is extremely high and may sometimes even loss full quantum of money invested. So, for the pensioners at Velur, it is worthy to study and analyze the investment pattern found in the stock market and then take decisions whether to invest or not. Investors should make the investment with proper planning keeping in mind their investment objectives. They must be provided with adequate awareness on the stock market instruments, its volatility, benefits so that they may get attracted towards the same through safer zones. Investors should also consult with the brokers or agents to seek information and advice but their decision should not merely be based on agent's advice, rather the decision should be based on their careful investigation. The investors should select a particular investment option on basis of their need and risk tolerance. They should diversify their investment portfolio in order to reduce the risk and should continuously monitor their investments.

Conclusion

Every investor prefers to invest in financial instruments that ensure better rewards with negligible risk. Large numbers of portfolio is not at all good for healthy investment. In India, a considerable percentage of citizens are aware of stock market games and its effective functioning. Majority of them purchases gold and land as investment that are considered to be most ideal form of investment as it carries good return and appreciation. This confirms that that Indian investors even if they are high income class, well educated, salaried, independent are conservative, still investors prefer to play safe.

As the inflationary position of the economy is stepping upwards from the past years and still increasing from time to time, the rate of return should ensure a cover against the inflation. The returns must be higher than the rate of inflation; otherwise the investor will have loss in real terms. The return thus earned should assure the safety of the principal amount, regular flow of income and be a hedge against inflation. Thus while selecting an investment avenue, one have to match their

own risk profile with the risks associated with the product before investing.

Every individual in service have to walk through the path of retirement after attaining a certain age which is gradual process in one's life and have to shape their life accordingly in their retired phase. So it becomes utmost necessary for an individual to reduce their public expenditures and concentrate more in investment avenues for their remaining part of life. For this, an appropriate investment strategy has to be adopted by analysing each and every investment opportunities that are available in the market, scrutinize the same and adopt a combination of three to four patterns for getting attractive return which in turn help to spent a comfortable retired life.

References

- PunithavathyPandian, Security analysis and portfolio management, Vikas Publishing house Pvt Ltd.
- C.R. Kothari, Research Methodology
- Prasanna Chandra, investment analysis and portfolio management, Tata McGraw Hill Education Pvt Ltd.
- Syed Tabassum Sultana, An Empirical Study on Indian individual investor's behaviour, Indian Journal of Finance
- P.Sashikala and R Siva Prasad Ravi, "A Study on the Effect of Demographic on the choice of Investments and Ability to take risk". Review of Business and Technology, Research Vol. 3, No. 1, 2010, ISSN 1941-9414
- Ms. M. KothaiNayaki and Mrs.P.Prema, "A Study on Indian Individual Investors' Behavior". Indian Journal of Finance
- V. ShanmugaSundaram and V. BalaKrishnan, "Investment decision-making – a behavioral approach", International Journal of Business innovation & Research vol.4, www.indiamoney.com
www.moneymanagementideas.com
www.investopedia.com
http://www.ijmra.us